

Version 1

**HEAD IMPACT VIDEO
EVALUATION (HIVE)
QUESTIONNAIRE AND
INSTRUCTIONS**

A. INTRODUCTION TO HIVE VIDEO ANALYSIS

The Head Impact Video Evaluation (HIVE) is a tool for reviewing video footage to identify the circumstance of head impacts in ice hockey. An individual rater will analyze various characteristics of the impact, probed through the HIVE. For each question, instructions are included that provide definitions, interpretations, and guidelines to assist the rater in completing the question.

In completing the HIVE, the rater should view the video footage on a high-quality computer screen (or LCD projector). The analysis should be completed in a quiet, private room. In analyzing the impact, the rater may view the video footage as many times as desired at any speed desired.

Details on the development and inter-rater reliability of the HIVE can be found in **Appendix B** of the following dissertation:

Aguiar, O. (2022). Biomechanics of head impacts in men's university ice hockey. [SFU Summit Research Repository](#).

B. GENERAL GUIDELINES FOR COMPLETING THE HIVE

These general guidelines should be followed while completing the HIVE:

- Select the single most appropriate answer to each question.
- There are no “can’t tell” answers. Instead, identify the single best answer to each question, and provide an estimate of the percent probability (between 1-100%) of that answer being correct. This probability will sometimes be quite low, as in the case, for example of substantial occlusion of body parts from the camera view. Select the probability in 5% increments. Here is a guide to help you determine what percentage to choose:
 - 100%: confident of the answer without a doubt;
 - 90%: confident of the answer with only a slight doubt;
 - 80%: confident of the answer with some doubt;
 - 70%: confident of the answer with reasonable doubt;
 - 60%: confident of the answer with considerable doubt;
 - 50%: confident of the answer but another answer or combination of answers could be equally plausible;
 - <40%: this is your best guess to the answer, in cases where you really can’t identify a single most probable answer.
- At the start of the session, play the video file through completely. Then play desired segments of the video as many times as desired to answer each question. Although the rater will likely wish to focus on only the few seconds surrounding the impact, the video may contain footage before and after the impact.
- Always play the video clip with the sound off. Video clips may include a narrated commentary. Please ensure the sound is off, to ensure the commentary does not influence the way you answer the questions.

C. DETAILED INSTRUCTIONS AND DEFINITIONS FOR EACH ITEM IN THE HIVE

1. Identification

Provide information on the video code, the name of the rater, and the date for completing the review of this video.

Video code: _____

Name of rater: _____

Date: _____

Part I: Situational factors at the instant of head impact

NOTE: All questions in this section focus on the player who RECEIVED the head impact

2. Was the head the first body site to be impacted in the collision (initial point of contact)?

Instructions: Describe whether or not the player's head was the initial point of meaningful contact during the primary impact.

- a) Yes b) No

Probability: _____

3. What body part or object struck the head during the PRIMARY contact?

Instructions: Answer this question even if you specified "no" to Question (2) above. Specify the body part of the checker, or the object, that first contacted the player's head in a significant manner. If "other" is selected, clearly describe in writing the body part or object. If there was no contact to the head, choose option (m). Note: The "caprail" is the ledge between the boards and the glass.

- a) Shoulder
b) Upper arm
c) Elbow
d) Forearm
e) Hands
f) Hip
g) Stick
h) Boards / Caprail
i) Glass
j) Ice
k) Net
l) Other: _____
m) No primary contact to the head

Probability: _____

4(a). Was there a second contact to the head? (e.g. after the first head contact)?

Instructions: Describe whether the head experienced a second significant impact (occurring after the first significant impact to the head).

- a) Yes
- b) No

Probability: _____

4(b). What body part or object struck the head in the SECOND contact?

Instructions: Specify the body part of the checker, or the object, that contacted the player's head during the second impact. If "other" is selected, clearly describe in writing the body part or object. If there was no second contact to the head, choose option (m). Note: The "caprail" is the ledge between the boards and the glass.

- a) Shoulder
- b) Upper arm
- c) Elbow
- d) Forearm
- e) Hands
- f) Hip
- g) Stick
- h) Boards / Cap rails
- i) Glass
- j) Ice
- k) Net
- l) Other: _____
- m) No second contact to the head

Probability: _____

5(a). Was there a third contact to the head? (e.g. after the primary and secondary collisions)?

Instructions: Describe whether the head experienced a third significant impact (occurring after the second significant impact to the head).

- a) Yes
- b) No

Probability: _____

5(b). What body part or object struck the head in the THIRD contact?

Instructions: Specify the body part of the checker, or the object, that contacted the player's head during the third impact. If "other" is selected, clearly describe in writing the body part or object. If there was no second contact to the head, choose option (m). Note: The "caprail" is the ledge between the boards and the glass.

- a) Shoulder
- b) Upper arm

- c) Elbow
- d) Forearm
- e) Hands
- f) Hip
- g) Stick
- h) Boards / Cap rails
- i) Glass
- j) Ice
- k) Net
- l) Other: _____
- m) No third contact to the head

Probability: _____

6. What aspect of the head received the impact in the PRIMARY contact?

Instructions: Specify the aspect of the head that was impacted during the primary contact to the head. The letters in the diagrams below point to the aspects that correspond to each answer below.

- a) Left lateral aspect of the head
- b) Right lateral aspect of the head
- c) Top (crown) of the head
- d) Back of the head
- e) Front of the head
- f) No contact to the head

Probability: _____

Part II: Situational factors preceding head impact

NOTE: All questions in this section focus on the player who RECEIVED the head impact

8. Did the player appear to be looking in the direction of the impending (initial) collision?

Instructions: Specify whether the player who received the check appeared to be looking in the direction of the checking player (or object) just before the primary contact to the head (initial collision), and therefore could have seen the impending collision.

- a) Yes (player was looking towards impending collision)
- b) No (player was not looking towards impending collision)

Probability: _____

9. Did the player receiving the check have possession of the puck when the initial collision occurred with the checking player or object?

Instructions: Select the option that best describes the relationship of the checked player to the puck at the time of the initial collision that resulted in primary head contact. Select “yes” if the player definitely had control of the puck. Select “attempting to gain possession of the puck” if the player is reaching or attempting to control the puck (e.g., in a struggle for the puck along the boards, or about to receive a pass). Select “had just released the puck” if the player had definite control of the puck prior to the impact but had lost or released the puck before the impact occurred (e.g. they had just passed the puck to another player). “No” would refer to a situation where the player did not have control of the puck and was not attempting to gain possession of it nor did they just release it (e.g. tipping a pass or shot, chipping a loose puck out).

- a) Yes (receiving player had possession of the puck at the time of the collision causing primary head contact)
- b) No (receiving player did not have possession of the puck at the time of the collision causing primary head contact)
- c) Receiving player was attempting to gain possession of the puck at the time of the collision causing primary head contact
- d) Receiving player had just released the puck at the time of the collision causing primary head contact

Probability: _____

10. In what playing zone did the initial collision occur with the checking player or object?

Instructions: Select the option that best describes the location on the ice of the player at the time of the initial collision that resulted in primary head contact. The defensive zone refers to the area of the ice that contains the net of the checked player's team, up to the blue line. The neutral zone refers to the area of ice between the blue lines. The offensive zone refers to the area of ice that contains the opposing team's net, up to the blue line. If the check occurs right on the blue line, select the region where the puck was headed). Note: the figure on the right labels each zone assuming the net for the checked player's team is on the left side.

- a) The defensive zone of the checked player's team
- b) The neutral zone
- c) The offensive zone of the checked player's team

Probability: _____

11. In what area of the ice did the head impact occur?

Instructions: Select the option that best describes the location on the ice of the player at the time of the initial collision that resulted in primary head contact.

- a) Along the side boards
- b) Near but not contacting the side boards
- c) Along the corner boards
- d) Near but not contacting the corner boards
- e) Open ice
- f) Near the net (crease)
- g) Along the end board/behind the net

Probability: _____

Part III: Situational factors proceeding head impact

NOTE: All questions in this section focus on the player who RECEIVED the head impact

12. Did the checked player appear affected by the head impact?

Instructions: Select the option that best describes if the player appeared affected by the head impact and note the probability.

a) Yes, the head impact caused a noticeable effect on player (visible sign(s) of concussion, pain or being "shaken up," may or may not return to play immediately)

a) No, the head impact caused little or no discernible effect on the player (no visible sign of concussion, pain or being "shaken up," returned to play immediately)

Probability: _____